

Kinetics and phase analysis of kesterite compounds: influence of chalcogen availability in the reaction pathway

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ABSTRACT

1 Physical vapor deposition methodologies have gained a lot of interest in the synthesis of kesterites,
2 including sequential processes based on sputtering of metals followed by reactive annealing. Bearing this
3 in mind, understanding the intermediate phases and possible formation routes of these techniques is
4 essential for their further progress. In this work, we have implemented innovative experiments to
5 demonstrate the strong interrelationship between the chalcogen availability in the annealing reactor and
6 the reaction pathways of kesterite formation. We present the first kinetics analysis of the selenization
7 process, including slow and fast ramped annealing steps. We observe that at low-medium chalcogen
8 availabilities, kesterite is formed following a pseudo-zero-order kinetics reaction which evolves towards
9 a first-order one with longer annealing times, mainly controlled by the reaction of binary phases. By
10 increasing the chalcogen availability, the kinetics is identified as a first-order one, evolving to a simpler
11 reaction pathway involving the ternary Cu_2SnSe_3 compound with ZnSe . Nevertheless, our results show
12 that, although to a marginal extent, the route involving the binary compounds is always competing with
13 the latter. The phase analysis is extended to the sulfur case, showing the similarities and differences of
14 both chalcogenization processes. This work expands the understanding of the formation reactions and
15 opens interesting perspectives for improving the kesterite synthesis.
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40 **Keywords:** kesterite; $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$; kinetics; chalcogenization; phase analysis; thin film photovoltaics
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1. Introduction

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47 Different thin film PV technologies are currently competing with wafer-based Si technologies for
48 reaching a share of the rapidly growing PV market. The inorganic thin film technologies $\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})\text{Se}_2$
49 (CIGS) and CdTe have obtained record efficiencies of 23.35% and 22.1% [1], respectively. Although
50 possessing the records efficiencies in the thin film PV technologies, CIGS and CdTe also have several
51 culprits as CIGS contains two critical raw materials (indium and gallium) and CdTe one (tellurium),
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1 which ends up into serious concerns for the PV community as it may develop in a shortage of materials
2 in a relatively near future [2].

3 In the view of new PV technologies that are formed by non-critical and non-toxic materials, kesterite
4 quaternary compounds ($\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ -CZTS or $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ -CZTSe or their corresponding solid solution
5 $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S,Se})_4$ -CZTSSe), are considered among the most promising candidates [3, 4]. This family of
6 materials has been widely studied in recent years, showing a very high light absorption coefficient of over
7 10^4 cm^{-1} , an intrinsic p-type conductivity, and a direct band gap ranging from 1.0 to 1.5 eV depending on
8 the S/Se content [3, 5, 6], making them ideally suited for PV applications.
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10 Kesterite, in common to other thin film chalcogenide technologies, share a high degree of flexibility
11 with the selection of methodologies for the synthesis of good quality absorbers. Historically, photovoltaic
12 devices fabricated with absorbers prepared by chemical routes [7-10] involving precursors that already
13 contain chalcogen, have shown better performances than those synthesized by physical based routes [11-
14 13]. This is slightly changing considering that physical vapor deposition routes have shown enormous
15 progresses in the last years, matching the conversion efficiencies reported by chemical ones [14-19].
16 Among them, the route involving sputtering of metallic stacks followed by a reactive annealing is
17 experiencing impressive advances, thanks to the better control of the formation of secondary phases and
18 homogeneity [14, 16, 20, 21]. Nevertheless, and in spite of these progresses, a better understanding of the
19 mechanisms and kinetic involved in the chalcogenization of metallic stacks is of primary importance for
20 improving the properties of the corresponding absorbers.
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22 Due to the relevance of sequential processes, several efforts have been made in order to start to
23 understand all the possible intermediate phases and reaction pathways for the formation of kesterite using
24 these techniques. Reaction either between binary compounds or between ternary and binary ones have
25 been proposed for this system [20]. The prevalence of one or other reaction is not clear until now, but
26 seems to depend on the conditions not only of the reactive annealing process, but also on the type of
27 precursor [20, 22, 23]. Apparently, when the precursor already contains chalcogen the route involving the
28 ternary compound is the preferred one, but when the precursor is chalcogen free the route involving the
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1 binary compounds is commonly reported [20]. Nevertheless, most of the available literature deals only
2 with thermodynamic and phase analysis aspects of these systems [24-28], because kinetic aspects are very
3 difficult to evaluate. Even for CIGS there is very limited information on the reaction kinetics of sequential
4 processing [29-34], with generic studies using mainly precursors already containing chalcogen or limited
5 to theoretical analysis.
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10 In the case of kesterites, Bodeaux et al. studied the selenization of co-sputtered Cu-Zn-Sn precursors,
11 suggesting that the kinetics of the reaction between Sn and Se is slower than the corresponding one
12 between Cu and Se, and that probably this is the limiting step in the reaction rate of CZTSe formation
13 [35]. On the other hand, Qu et al. studied the selenization kinetics of CZTSSe nanoparticles using the
14 parabolic grain growth and Avrami models [36]. These methodologies are mainly useful for
15 understanding grain growth process or chalcogen diffusion, but gives limited information about the
16 reaction types and their corresponding kinetic parameters, although these can be very relevant at the early
17 stages of the compound formation. This information combined with a thermodynamic phase analysis can
18 be then very helpful to understand and overcome possible synthesis limitations in the system.
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32 This work focuses on a combined kinetics and phase analysis investigation which leads to a better
33 understanding of the formation pathways of kesterite absorbers during the very early stages of the
34 synthesis process. To do so, we stop the reactive annealing (chalcogenization of sputtered metallic stacks)
35 at different temperatures and times, comparing both fast and slow ramping processes, and investigate the
36 chalcogen availability as this is identified to be the most relevant annealing parameter. Using simple
37 compositional measurements, we establish the first kinetic analysis of the pure selenide kesterite formation
38 and extract important parameters such as the reaction order, kinetic constant and reaction half-time. In
39 addition, we combine multi-wavelength Raman spectroscopy (RS) and X-Ray diffraction (XRD) to
40 perform a complete phase analysis, which we then correlate to the kinetic regimes where the phases are
41 formed. Finally, we present a preliminary extension of this phase analysis for the pure sulfide kesterite
42 formation during slow ramping annealing condition.
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2. Materials and Methods

1 Soda lime glass (SLG) substrates were conditioned via a mechanical cleaning with special soap and
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3 subjected to a 50 °C ultrasonic bath cleaning process with the following solvents sequence: acetone,
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5 isopropanol and deionized water during 10 min for each of them. Mo back contact layers (800 nm, 0.3
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7 $\Omega/\square$) were deposited by pulsed DC-magnetron sputtering (Alliance Concept CT100) immediately after
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9 the cleaning process. The synthesis of CZTSe and CZTS films was performed by a sequential process,
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11 based first on the deposition of Cu/Sn/Cu/Zn metallic precursor stacks by DC-magnetron sputtering
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13 (Alliance Concept Ac-450) onto the previously Mo coated SLG substrates. The composition of the films
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15 was inside the range of those reported as ideal for high-efficiency solar cell devices, namely Cu-poor and
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17 Zn-rich: $Cu/(Zn + Sn) = 0.77$, $Zn/Sn = 1.21$, $Cu/Zn = 1.41$, and $Cu/Sn = 1.71$.
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23 Then, the metallic precursors (2.5 x 2.5 cm² in area) were selenized or sulfurized either using a fast-
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25 ramping processes in a rapid thermal annealing (RTP) system, or a slow thermal ramping using a
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27 conventional tubular furnace (CTP). In this work, we introduce a parameter related to the chalcogen vapor
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29 pressure, defined as chalcogen availability (ChA). The sample area and precursor thickness were kept
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31 constant. In order to compare the different annealing setups, we define ChA as the ratio between
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33 chalcogen amount and reactor volume: $ChA = mCh(g)/VGB(cm^3)$, where mCh is the mass of chalcogen
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35 (S or Se) used during the experiment in grams, and VGB is the volume of the graphite box in cubic
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37 centimeters.
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42 The RTP samples were selenized using an AnnealSys AS-ONE-100 furnace in a semi-closed system
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44 made up by a graphite box with a reaction volume of 3.8 cm³. The annealing process consisted of heating
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46 from room temperature to the maximum temperature (400 °C, 350 °C, 300 °C, 250 °C and 200 °C were
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48 investigated), with a fast ramp (180 °C/min) and a total pressure of 1 mbar of Ar. The process was
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50 immediately stopped, and the system quickly cooled down once reached the maximum temperature. For
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52 some temperatures (250 °C, 300 °C and 350 °C), we also stopped the reaction at different times, namely
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54 after 20 s, 50 s, 80 s, 110 s, 140 s and 200 s. In addition, a set of samples with different Se availabilities
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56 were investigated, and, in particular, we focus our study in three types of regimes: low, medium and high
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Se availability. **Table 1** summarize the chalcogen amount used for the kinetic investigation. The use of six quantities respond to the necessity to have statistics and intermediate points to validate the presented kinetic models.

Table 1. Chalcogen availabilities (ChA) used in this work for the kinetic study.

Rapid thermal processing (RTP)	
Regimes	Chalcogen amount ($\text{g}_{\text{Se}}/\text{cm}^3$)
Low availability	2.6×10^{-4}
	1.32×10^{-3}
	2.64×10^{-3}
Medium availability	5.26×10^{-3}
	1.32×10^{-2}
High availability	2.64×10^{-2}
Conventional thermal processing (CTP)	
Regimes	Chalcogen amount ($\text{g}_{\text{Se (S)}}/\text{cm}^3$)
Low availability	7.20×10^{-5}
	7.20×10^{-4}
Medium availability	1.45×10^{-3}
	2.90×10^{-3}
High availability	7.20×10^{-3}
	1.45×10^{-2}

To study the influence of the heating ramp in the chalcogenization process, another set of samples were annealed under slow ramping conditions (CTP). For this, we use a tubular furnace that works with a Se + Sn atmosphere and S + Sn for CZTSe and CZTS samples, respectively. A semi-closed system made up by a graphite box with a reaction volume of 69 cm^3 was used at 1 mbar of Ar as total pressure, and heated from room temperature up to $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (either for Se and S) with a ramp of $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Chalcogen availabilities are summarized in **Table 1** for Se and S (extension to the CZTS case).

Annealed CZTSe and CZTS films were characterized by XRF in order to obtain their composition (Fisherscope XVD previously calibrated using ICP-OES) and by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, ZEISS Series Auriga microscope) for studying their morphology. In addition, a complete phase analysis was performed by the combination of XRD and RS. XRD measurements were performed using a PANalytical X'pert ProMPD diffractometer with Cu-K α -radiation ($\lambda=1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) and a secondary

1 graphite monochromator. Multi-wavelength RS measurements were performed in back scattering
2 configuration using a Horiba Jobin Yvon fHR-640 spectrometer for laser excitation at wavelengths 325
3 nm, 442 nm and 532 nm and an iHR-320 spectrometer at 785 nm. Spectrometers are coupled with RS
4 probes developed at IREC and a low noise CCD detector cooled to -70 °C. Excitation and light collection
5 were made using a macro-optic system with a laser spot diameter of the order of 50 μm. In order to avoid
6 thermal effects in the spectra, the power density on the surface of samples was kept below 150 W/cm².
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8 The position of all spectra has been corrected taking into account the first order RS spectrum of
9 monocrystalline silicon as a reference measured before each acquisition and imposing its position at 520
10 cm⁻¹.
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23 **3. Results and Discussion**

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25 In the first place, the kinetic study is approached from chalcogenization experiments using different
26 chalcogen availabilities, in fast (RTP, only Se) and slow ramped (CTP, Se and S) controlled annealing
27 experiments. A kinetic model is proposed quantifying the incorporation of chalcogen in the reaction
28 product. A complementary phase analysis and identification of intermediate compounds reveal kesterite
29 reaction pathways as a function of chalcogen availability during thermal processing. Finally, the analysis
30 extends to the reaction pathway of pure sulfide kesterite.
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41 **3.1. Cu₂ZnSnSe₄ reaction kinetics and phase analysis with different chalcogen availabilities**

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43 For high efficiency devices, chalcogenization is performed at 500-600 °C, but previous publications
44 have reported that kesterite formation already starts at temperatures between 300-400 °C [16, 20-22].
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46 Therefore, in these first experiments, the chalcogenization was carried out at 400 °C. **Figure 1** presents
47 the evolution of the elemental composition (Cu, Zn, Sn and Se) as a function of the ChA covering the
48 three different regimes (low, medium and high) defined in **Table 1**. Moreover, the influence of the heating
49 ramp is also depicted for fast (180 °C/min) and slow (20 °C/min) ramped annealing. By varying the
50 heating ramp speed, it aims to study two different types of thermal processes, one kinetic controlled (fast
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ramping), and the other where thermodynamics predominates (slow ramp). This approach is key to recognize differences and similarities between slow and fast processes, separating the kinetic and thermodynamic factors that can play a major role during the formation of these compounds.

Fig. 1. Evolution of the concentration of the different elements as determined by XRF for samples prepared with (a) fast ramping (180 °C/min), and (b) slow ramping (20 °C/min).

In more detail, from **Fig. 1(a)** (fast ramping process) incomplete selenization is observed for low chalcogen availabilities. Only when approaching medium or high chalcogen availabilities all the Se necessary to get stoichiometric kesterite is incorporated into the layer. An interesting contrast present slow ramped process, where the metallic precursors are completely selenized even for very low chalcogen availabilities (see **Fig. 1(b)**). This could be indicating that during a slow ramped annealing the chalcogenization process achieves an equilibrium and is completed in a relatively short time, which is in good agreement with previous reports [35]. In turn, this clearly points out that in a fast ramped process [**Fig. 1(a)**] the system is still out of equilibrium and probably under kinetic control, opening very interesting possibilities to perform a kinetic analysis. For kinetic, we need to define first a generic reaction that represents the formation of the kesterite. This can be represented as:

1 Where M represents the stacked metal layers with m as the stoichiometric factor in the reaction, Se_2 is the
2 selenium in the gas phase with n as its stoichiometric factor, and Ch represents the chalcogen formed with
3 x as its corresponding stoichiometric factor. T and t are temperature and time, respectively.
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5 The kinetic study of this reaction is complicated by the fact that it is a heterogenous reaction with solid
6 and gas phases involved together. In order to enable a first analysis of the system, we need to introduce
7 some logic assumptions and develop a simplified model, useful for the chalcogenization of metallic layers
8 as is described in the first section of the Supplementary Material (SM) file. Based on this simplified
9 model, we will elucidate which kinetic-order fits better for the different ChA regimes, trying to correlate
10 this with possible formation pathways.
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20 Usually, in order to carry out a kinetic study, in-situ experiments are used to monitor the progress of
21 the reaction. Chalcogenization is a reactive annealing process that involves harsh process conditions,
22 which complicates the implementation of in-situ experiments. In turn, in-situ characterization setups are
23 rarely able to replicate the exact experimental conditions of the process in which these materials are
24 synthesized. Moreover, the chalcogenization reaction is a relatively fast process, much faster than the
25 typical times necessary for a complete annealing process (of the order of several tens of minutes), even
26 under fast ramping conditions. Therefore, the application of the differential method for the determination
27 of the reaction-order is very challenging, requiring some assumptions. **Figure 2** shows “break off”
28 experiments where the Se concentration is measured in different samples whose RTP processes were
29 stopped at selected temperatures (200 °C, 250 °C, 300 °C, 350 °C and 400 °C; for this last temperature in
30 a different run than the one presented in **Fig. 1**), and using four different chalcogen availabilities (**Table**
31 **1**). Clearly, for temperatures below 250 °C the chalcogenization reaction does not proceed, or partially
32 proceed only under high chalcogen availabilities. From 400 °C, the reaction is practically completed (Se
33 close to 50%) at the very beginning, except for the low ChA regime where the precursor is partially
34 selenized. This leaves only the temperature range between 250-350 °C useful for the kinetic analysis. We
35 chose then 300 °C as the most suitable temperature for a deep kinetic analysis, considering that common
36 differential methods for kinetic analysis require isothermic conditions [37, 38].
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Fig. 2. Selenium concentration for the experiments performed using the RTP system. The reactive annealing was stopping at different temperatures and using different ChA values.

Our methodology for approaching the kinetic model of CZT metallic stacks selenization is based in the following assumptions:

- i. In the limited range of temperatures that we are using (in most cases 250-350 °C), the kesterite is the most stable phase [25, 39].
- ii. Most of the phases involved in the system are solid (and their concentrations can be considered independent of temperature) with the exception of Se vapor, which temperature variation is being considered with the measurement of chalcogen incorporation into the layers (product).
- iii. Selenium diffusion can be considered fast in the chalcogenide systems even at relatively low temperature and is enhanced by the presence of sodium [29, 40].

Normally, kinetic studies are based on monitoring the consumption of one of the reactants in the reaction. Indeed, kinetics integral equations normally are expressed using the decrease in concentration of reactant in time t [37]. In the selenization of the metal stack this is difficult to achieve, and in turn it cannot be ensured that all the available selenium manages to react with the metal stack. For these reasons, our approach is reversed, and our kinetic model proposes to address the reaction kinetic by tracking how much selenium is incorporated into the reaction product (kesterite) as the reaction progresses over time.

With this in mind, we can propose a simplified kinetic model for the generic reaction (1) to obtain an estimation of kinetic constants as well as the kinetic order of reaction. The kinetic model (Supplemental Material, section I) for the reaction presented in (1) can be simplified as:

$$\frac{d([Se]_{sat} - [Se]_K)}{dt} = xk_n([Se]_{sat} - [Se]_K)^n, \quad (2)$$

Where $[Se]_{sat}$ is the Se concentration (or number of moles) for an infinite-time reaction, $[Se]_K$ is the Se concentration (or number of moles) in the kesterite compound, and k_n is the kinetic constant corresponding to a reaction-order n . In fact, $([Se]_{sat} - [Se]_K)$ is the Se quantity required to end the reaction or, equivalent, the metallic phases consumed during the selenization. Using this general kinetic expression, we can fit the data with reactions of zero-, first- and second kinetic orders as it detailed in the SM. Error! Reference source not found. presents the kinetic analysis results obtained for low-medium and medium-high chalcogen availabilities, at 300 °C. Particularly for very high availabilities of chalcogen it is difficult to achieve a reliable kinetic study.

Fig3. Complete kinetic analysis of the selenization of metallic stacks using fast ramping (RTP). The fitting is presented for three different kinetic orders (zero, first and second order), as well as for two different chalcogen availabilities (low-medium and medium-high).

The reaction is so fast that the selenization of the metallic precursors is contemplated in very short times, difficult to monitor with our set-up. For low-medium ChA ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ g}_{\text{Se}}/\text{cm}^3$), three different kinetic orders are fitted (see upper part of **Fig. 3**), and a first-order kinetic presents the best fitting, most likely being the order of the reaction (**Table 2** summarize extracted fitting parameters). However, due to the good fitting shown by the first (four) points of the zero-order reaction, we do not rule out that the reaction starts following this reaction order. Nevertheless, this type of kinetic is often considered as a pseudo-state because it cannot continue after one of the involved reactants is exhausted. Normally, before going to zero, the reaction rate will change to another rate law in this case a first-order reaction [37]. Two conditions can lead to zero-order kinetic at the very beginning:

1) when only a small part of the reactants is in the state required to react but this small fraction is continually supported from the reactive source; and 2) when the concentration of one reactant is orders of magnitudes greater than the others. In our case, we can consider that the first condition better represents the system at the very beginning, because the Se quantity available for the reaction is limited in the range for low-medium ChA, but the Se is continuously supplied during the reaction time. Despite this, we can consider that in overall the selenization reaction proceed via a first order reaction.

The situation only slightly changes when we increase the ChA to the medium-high values as can be seen in the lower part of **Fig. 3**. In this case only the first four reaction times can be used because the system saturates (complete selenization) for longer annealing times. Newly, the best fitting is obtained supposing a first order kinetic, implying that the selenization rate is directly proportional to the ChA. This is the most expected situation, indicating that by controlling the ChA value we can control the selenization reaction rate. Higher reaction orders (second order) do not fit well in any condition, suggesting that the selenization process proceeds via a relatively simple mechanism. **Table II** summarizes also the main kinetic parameters extracted from **Fig. 3** for the different chalcogen availabilities, including the half-life

time ($t_{1/2}$) determined as is explained in the SM file. Half-life times ($t_{1/2}$) values help to confirm that the chalcogenization of the metallic stacks is a very fast process, typically requiring times in the order of minutes to be completed [13, 16, 20]. It is important to highlight that the kinetic parameters were obtained at a temperature of 300 °C, and that the true selenization in a RTP system is carried out at temperatures from 400 °C to 500 °C [20]. The kinetic constant k is then expected to be even higher (Arrhenius-type behavior), which would imply even shorter process times.

Table 2. Reaction kinetic parameters extracted from the fitting for the identified reaction-orders and for the different chalcogen availabilities.

Chalcogen availability	Probable reaction order	k_n (s^{-1})	$t_{1/2}$ (s)
Low-Medium	First (zero at the beginning)	$k_1 = (1.9 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-2}$	37
Medium-High	First	$k_1 = (2.9 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-2}$	24

To the best of our knowledge, we report for first time kinetic parameters for fast selenization (RTP) of stacked metallic precursors at 300 °C. We observe that this thermal reaction follows first-order kinetics in a wide range of chalcogen availability, pointing out a strong dependence between the reaction kinetics with this parameter (ChA). This means that the chalcogen reacts with the metallic matrix, regardless of the alloys that are formed (mainly bronzes and brass), or that the selenization of one of these metallic alloys is notably slower than the others, controlling the reaction kinetics. Additionally, we expect that this kinetic behavior does not depend on the type of ramping and this analysis can be transferred to slow ramping processes.

In the next step, we perform a complete morphology and phase analysis of samples whose composition was presented in **Fig. 1**. **Figure 4** shows SEM top view images for the two types of ramping processes under investigation, and for the whole range of chalcogen availabilities (the complete set of SEM images is presented in the SM, Section 2, **Fig. S1**). In the case of fast ramping, the surface morphology of the

sample prepared at low Se availability is very similar to the typical metallic precursor surface confirming a low Se incorporation [41]. The morphology changes with increasing Se availability as this is progressively incorporated into the metallic layers as expected. In all cases the layers look either amorphous or nanocrystalline, suggesting that crystallization has not started under these conditions. This reinforces the kinetic model presented before because it implies that all the Se incorporated in the samples was mainly used to diffuse into the metallic layer to form the kesterite and not to crystallize it.

Fig. 4. (a) Thermal profile and top view SEM images of absorbers generated with a fast ramp at different chalcogen availabilities. (b) Thermal profile and top view SEM images of absorbers generated slow ramp at different chalcogen availabilities (ChA).

Otherwise, samples selenized with slow ramp show morphologies with distinct, large crystals even for the case of low chalcogen availability. As ChA increases the crystals increase in size and density pointing out that the crystallization process requires much longer times than the synthesis process. For this reason, and to obtain high quality kesterites, the synthesis and crystallization (densification) of the material are carried out in decoupled stages, each with independent chalcogenization times, temperatures

and pressures [16, 42]. In addition, these differences in the surface morphology could also be associated to the presence of different phases. To investigate this, a complete phase analysis using combined Raman spectroscopy (RS) and XRD characterization techniques was performed.

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the phase analysis performed using RS and XRD for the whole chalcogen availability range, for fast ramp (a), and slow ramp (b) processes. Vertical white lines represent the chalcogen availability where the maximum signal intensity corresponding to this particular phase is detected. The intensity of the color correlates with the quantity of each phase.

Fig. 5 shows a schematic representation of the different phases identified by XRD and RS for fast and slow ramps. The data plotted was obtained from the characterizations presented in the SM (Section 3, **Fig. S3, S4, S5** and **S6**). In **Fig. 5** the chalcogen availability for whom the maximum intensity for each phase is obtained, is represented with a vertical white line. The intensity of the RS and XRD signals corresponding to each phase has been represented by the color graduation. In addition, and for helping

with the discussion, in **Table 3** all the detected phases under the different experimental conditions are summarized.

Table 3. Summary of the detected phases extracted from **Fig.5** depending on the chalcogen availability regime. (-) – Not detected. (+) – Present but in small quantities. (++) – Present in high quantities. (?) – Not clear.

Thermal process	Chalcogen availability (mg/cm ³)		
	Low (ChA < 1x10 ⁻³)	Medium (1x10 ⁻³ ≤ ChA ≤ 1x10 ⁻²)	High (ChA > 1x10 ⁻²)
Fast ramping (Kinetics control)	Cu-Se: (-)	Cu-Se: (-), or (?)	Cu-Se: (-)
	ZnSe: (++)	ZnSe: (++)	ZnSe: (++)
	Sn-Se: (++)	Sn-Se: (+)	Sn-Se: (+)
	Cu-Sn-Se: (-)	Cu-Sn-Se: (++)	Cu-Sn-Se: (+)
	Cu ₂ ZnSnSe ₄ : (+)	Cu ₂ ZnSnSe ₄ : (+)	Cu ₂ ZnSnSe ₄ : (++)
	Metals: (+) (bronze), (?) (brasses)	Metals: (-)	Metals: (-)
Slow ramping (Thermodynamic control)	Cu-Se: (++)	Cu-Se: (++)	Cu-Se: (++)
	ZnSe: (++)	ZnSe: (++)	ZnSe: (++)
	Sn-Se: (++)	Sn-Se: (++)	Sn-Se: (+)
	Cu-Sn-Se: (-)	Cu-Sn-Se: (++)	Cu-Sn-Se: (++)
	Cu ₂ ZnSnSe ₄ : (-), or (?)	Cu ₂ ZnSnSe ₄ : (+)	Cu ₂ ZnSnSe ₄ : (++)
	Metals: (++) (Sn)	Metals: (++) (Sn)	Metals: (++) (Sn)

For low-medium chalcogen availabilities, where we identify most probably a pseudo-zero-order kinetic as the most probable selenium incorporation mechanism at the very beginning and then evolving to a first-order kinetic, only a mix of metallic and binary-chalcogenide phases are observed for both: fast and slow ramping. This strongly posits that the reaction of binary phases is the preferential pathway for the formation of kesterite under such conditions (low ChA). As a possible reaction layout, fully

compatible with a zero- or first- order kinetic, the limited selenium in the precursor surface reacts indistinctly with the immediate available metal forming the simplest and fastest species (binary phases). Main differences between fast or slow processes are only related to the type of metallic phases present in the system. Apparently, for fast ramping annealing, only complex metallic phases (bronzes and maybe brasses) are presented (there is not enough time for further phase transformation), suggesting that Se reacts directly with them following:

as an expected selenization reaction of bronzes under fast ramping and low chalcogen availability, and (4) of brasses under low chalcogen availability independently on the heating ramp.

It is interesting what happens in slow ramped processes. Free metallic Sn is detected through XRD analysis. This is in agreement with previous reports in which metallic Sn is frequently observed for slow ramp annealing during the early stages of kesterite synthesis [23, 25]. This could be formed through

that produces a phase change towards a Cu-rich composition releasing metallic tin as a by-product (5).

Then, the resulting Cu-rich bronze selenizes directly following

as a selenization reaction of bronzes under slow ramp and low chalcogen availability. Basically, we can infer that for fast ramping processes the bronze metallic phases appear to be directly selenized, whereas when we "let the thermodynamics work" (slow ramping), bronzes can undergo phase changes during the selenization process, leaving unreacted phases (mostly metallic Sn). In the case of brass, we cannot extract precise information from XRD because this phase as well as Zn and Cu metallic phases of are hardly observed, so we assume that even with very low ChA, Cu-Zn alloys are directly selenized (4). Then of

course, the only way to form kesterite under such conditions is through the reaction of the binary chalcogenide compounds, and one possibility is

as the most probable formation reaction for kesterite at low chalcogen availability. Certainly, bearing in mind the complex Cu-Se and Sn-Se phase diagrams the competence with other possible binary compounds coming from these systems cannot be discarded, but the general schema will not change, and the possible competing reactions will always be a complex solid-state reaction. In summary, we can conclude that when low amounts of chalcogen atoms are available to the system, the kesterite is formed mainly via a binary phases reaction independently on the type of heating ramps. The only difference when using slow ramping processes lies in the fact that there is time for the bronzes to decompose (at least partially) when are being selenized, which does not seem to occur in fast ramping processes. All these metallic phases are indistinctly selenized probably via a zero-order reaction at the very beginning that rapidly evolves towards a first order kinetics. Obviously, to work under low chalcogen availabilities is not recommended at all, considering the high risk to have unreacted binary-selenide and even metallic phases at the end of the selenization process, together with the complexity of the mechanisms involved in the formation of kesterite.

The situation is radically different when the chalcogen availability is increased to values considered medium or high. As was shown before, the kinetic mechanism changes are in this case better explained via a first order reaction with a relatively high kinetic constant and relatively lower $t_{1/2}$ value. This means that the reaction is accelerated and Se reacts very fast with any kind of metallic phase available in the system. This is clearly seen in **Fig. 5** and **Table 3**, where the Cu_3SnSe_2 (CTSe) ternary phase becomes the most relevant so far and no metallic phases are observed at all for fast ramping, while only Sn is observed for slow ramping. So, in principle we can consider that in this case, bronzes and brasses react directly with selenium to form the intermediates. In particular, for fast ramping the selenization of bronze occurs most probably through

where the ternary Cu_2SnSe_3 is directly formed, but inevitably together with Sn-Se phases at the same time. This is very significant, because it manifests that binary Sn-Se phases are necessarily always formed, independently on the selenization route followed by the bronze alloy. Brasses only have the possibility to react via (4), where Cu-Se and ZnSe are the resulting phases. This brings us to the first general conclusion for medium-high chalcogen availabilities and fast ramps. Even if in such conditions we can transform the synthesis route of CZTSe involving in this case more complex phases like the ternary compound, it is impossible to avoid the presence of simplest binary compounds as competitors. The situation does not change too much when slow ramps are used. Still, elemental Sn is observed always, even for very high chalcogen availabilities inferring that reaction (5) (i.e., transformation of Cu_6Sn_5 into Cu_3Sn) is in general faster than the selenization of bronzes. Then, Cu_3Sn is directly selenized forming the ternary compound given by

Then, in that case due to the presence of high quantities of ternary Cu_2SnSe_3 compound the formation of kesterite can proceed via the reaction of the ternary compound with ZnSe as is described in

as the most probable formation reaction for kesterite at medium-high chalcogen availability.

Nevertheless, as is clear from (8) and (9), as well as **Fig. 5** and **Table 3**, the presence of binary phases including Cu-Se and Sn-Se ones is almost unavoidable and have been detected at some time in all the possible kesterite formation pathways independently on the chalcogen availability and the type of reaction kinetics. This implies that, for medium and high chalcogen availability reaction (10) is the prevalent mechanism for kesterite formation. However, the reaction via (7) is always present and competing, although probably to a much lesser extent as the chalcogen availability increases. As a summary, we demonstrate that for low chalcogen availabilities the binary route with a pseudo-zero-order kinetics

1 evolving to a first-order one for longer times is largely preferred, and for medium-high chalcogen
2 availabilities the synthesis route via ternaries with a first-order kinetic is the prevalent, but competing
3 with the binary route that seems to be unavoidable.
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6 This opens very important perspectives for the synthesis of kesterites using sequential processes where
7 the precursors are metallic stacks. Independently on the precursor type and the chalcogenization
8 conditions, the presence of undesired binary phases (Cu-Se and Sn-Se) can be minimized, but not 100%
9 removed. At high chalcogen availabilities the quantity of these phases seems to be strongly reduced,
10 although never eliminated. We consider this to be the better condition to synthesize homogeneous
11 absorbers. Nevertheless, and in order to ensure the lowest possible quantity of secondary phases after the
12 end of the synthesis process, it is recommended to take additional measures such as: 1) ensure a high
13 degree of intermixture between the metallic precursors, 2) ensure enough annealing time to let the reaction
14 finish, and 3) post-deposition treatments are probably useful for the diffusion and termination of the
15 reaction of these unreacted phases.
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30 All this strongly suggests that, despite the latest impressive progresses achieved with this type of
31 synthetic routes, it is very difficult if not impossible to obtain kesterite absorbers free of secondary phases
32 using the chalcogenization of elemental metallic precursors. Nevertheless, further improvements can be
33 expected in the future by using precursors with a better mix of the different metals (complex precursors
34 using alloys instead of separated elements), better control of the chalcogen availability (temperature,
35 pressure), and/or combination with precursors already containing chalcogen. An interesting approach was
36 recently reported by Pareek et al, where the elemental Sn layer in the precursor stack is replaced with a
37 sputtered Cu-Sn alloy [21,22]. The modification of the precursor composition in combination with an
38 optimized selenization stage, helps in avoiding the formation and subsequent evaporation of SnSe_{2-x}
39 phases, improving the final Sn composition in the absorber. A simple inclusion of a Cu-Sn alloy alters
40 the pathway of kesterite formation proving that there is a long way to go in the synthesis of this complex
41 material.
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3.2. Preliminary extension for sulfur-based kesterite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$)

We performed some additional experiments in order to extend the previous kinetic analysis to the case of sulfur-based kesterites. As we have done before, the reactive annealing process was also stopped at 400 °C, applying only a slow ramp (20 °C/min), once again covering the full chalcogen availability range. **Fig. 6** shows the evolution of the different elemental concentrations with the increased chalcogen availability, analogue to **Fig. 1b**. Notably, even for high S amounts the sulfurization reaction is not completed at the investigated temperature, suggesting that the sulfurization is a much slower process than the selenization one. This is in principle intuitively contrary to the expected trend: sulfur has a much higher vapor pressure and sulfur vapors are normally more reactive than selenium ones. Even at very high chalcogen availabilities ($> 0.01 \text{ g}_s/\text{cm}^3$), the sulfur content in the layer tends to saturate at 42% under the studied experimental conditions. In fact, the morphological changes observed by SEM allow us to confirm these differences between the sulfurized and selenized processes. The morphological changes of the metal precursor start with very low ChA values in the presence of selenium (**Fig S1b** in the SM). On the other hand, only the sulfurized metal precursors at high ChA values present morphological changes that show the formation of kesterite or related intermediate phases (**Fig. S1c**).

Fig.6. Evolution of the concentration of the different elements as determined by XRF for samples sulfurized under slow ramping conditions (20 °C/min).

All these CZTS samples produced with different chalcogen availabilities were characterized by RS and XRD. The complete set of Raman spectra with different excitation wavelengths as well as the XRD patterns are presented in Fig. S7 and S8 in the SM. The evolution of the different phases is graphically schematized in Fig. 7, and summarized in Table 4. In the case of the sulfur compound, for low chalcogen

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the phase analysis performed using RS and XRD for the whole chalcogen availability range for CZTS. Vertical white lines represent the chalcogen availability where the maximum intensity of this phase is registered.

availabilities a complex mix of metallic phases (bronzes, brasses and free Sn) are mainly present, together with notable amounts of ZnS. This corroborates the lower reactivity of sulfur with respect to Se, and that this chalcogen reacts very selectively with Zn forming ZnS, which is the most stable phase in this system. Most probably kesterite is not formed due to the absence of Cu-S and Sn-S binary phases, because we

expect that for these conditions the binaries route for the formation of kesterite prevails. The quantity of metallic phases starts to be drastically reduced at medium chalcogen availabilities. Other sulfide phases different than ZnS are observed including SnS and Cu₂SnS₃ and small amounts of kesterite. This again

Table 4. Summary of the detected phases extracted from Fig. 7 depending on the chalcogen availability regime. (-) – Not detected. (+) – Present but in small quantities. (++) – Present in high quantities. (?) – Not clear.

Thermal process	Chalcogen availability (mg/cm ³)		
	Low (ChA < 1x10 ⁻³)	Medium (1x10 ⁻³ ≤ ChA ≤ 1x10 ⁻²)	High (ChA > 1x10 ⁻²)
Slow ramping (Thermodynamic control)	Cu-S: (-)	Cu-S: (-) or few	Cu-S: (-)
	ZnS: (++)	ZnS: (++)	ZnS: (++)
	Sn-S: (-)	Sn-S: (+)	Sn-S: (+)
	Cu-Sn-S: (-)	Cu-Sn-S: (++)	Cu-Sn-S: (+)
	Cu ₂ ZnSnS ₄ : (-)	Cu ₂ ZnSnS ₄ : (+)	Cu ₂ ZnSnS ₄ : (++)
	Metals: (+) (bronze), (+) (brasses), (-) (Sn)	Metals: (+) (bronze), (+) (brasses), (+) (Sn)	Metals: (-) or (?) (Sn)

suggest that for medium chalcogen availability the formation pathway involving the ternary compounds is the preferred route similarly to what was observed for the selenide compound. By increasing ChA to values considered high, an early kesterite formation is promoted with strong reduction of the Cu₂SnS₃ and ZnS signals. This indicates an accelerated formation of CZTS under such conditions, but again both possible pathways including binaries and the ternary compound are probably competing as in the case of the selenides. The data presented here indicates that the formation pathways of sulfur and selenium compounds are very similar, although some differences are observed mainly in the dynamic of the processes suggesting that the kinetic of sulfurization of metallic stacks is somehow different and slower than the one observed for the selenides.

4. Conclusion

We performed a combined kinetic and phase analysis of the chalcogenization process of metallic precursor stacks used for the synthesis of high quality kesterite absorbers. Slow and fast ramps were investigated for the selenization reaction with different chalcogen availabilities (from low to high ChA). Under low-medium chalcogen availability, the selenization process seems to proceed via a pseudo-zero-order kinetic reaction that evolves towards a first-order one for relatively long annealing times, with a constant equal to $k_1 = (1.9 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a $t_{1/2} = 37 \text{ s}$. In such conditions, mainly binary compounds are formed as intermediate species for the final formation of kesterites. When the chalcogen availability is increased up to values considered medium-high, the selenization process proceeds via a first-order kinetic reaction, with a kinetic constant about $k_1 = (2.9 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and a $t_{1/2} = 24 \text{ s}$. This demonstrates that the selenization reaction is accelerated, and we found that under such conditions the preferred pathway to form kesterite is via the reaction between ternary Cu_2SnSe_3 and binary ZnSe compounds, simplifying the formation route of CZTSe. This is a clear advantage, as it reduces the occurrence of unreacted secondary phases after the selenization is finished. Nevertheless, and despite the high chalcogen availability, the synthesis route involving binary compounds is still observed, although to a much lower extent. Additional strategies are required for ensuring high quality absorbers free of secondary phases using this approach.

A first extension towards the sulfide kesterites showed similarities in terms of phases observed, with the route involving binaries being the preferred one for low ChA, and the one involving the Cu_2SnS_3 ternary for high ChA. While the sulfurization process still requires a more detailed kinetic analysis, it is already obvious that it is a much slower process when compared to the selenization.

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25 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

26 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
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